

HIV SENTINEL SURVEILLANCE (ANC)

Andhra Pradesh State Report

2014-15

ICMR-NATIONAL
INSTITUTE OF EPIDEMIOLOGY
Chennai

NATIONAL
AIDS CONTROL ORGANISATION
New Delhi

ANDHRA PRADESH
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Suggested citation

ICMR - National Institute of Epidemiology (2018). HIV Sentinel Surveillance 2014-15, Andhra Pradesh State Report: Indian Council of Medical Research, Department of Health Research, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India.

ISSN 2583-2336

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Foreword

HIV Sentinel surveillance among ANC attendees is one of the most important national level activities, as it helps the programme managers in framing health policies towards controlling HIV infection in the state and the country as well. The objectives of HIV sentinel surveillance are to understand the trends, assess spread and distribution of HIV infection among geographical areas across the state. In order to have uniform geographical coverage, the number of sentinel sites in the state has been increased over a period of years by keeping at least one site in each district.

The National Institute of Epidemiology, Chennai, one of the Regional Institutes for 8 southern states, is involved in the HIV surveillance activities since 2006. This report is prepared based on the data collected during the 14th round of surveillance, in conjunction with the past years data to analyze the trend and to have an insight of epidemiological factors. I hope this report will serve as a very useful tool for the policy makers, scholars, researchers and other stakeholders in formulating guidelines in controlling HIV and enhancing their knowledge of HIV in their state.

I take this opportunity to thank Dr. S. Venkatesh, Deputy Director General, NACO and Dr. Pradeep Kumar, Consultant (surveillance) & his team for entrusting this activity to NIE and also for providing technical support in implementing the surveillance. I also wish to thank the Project Director and nodal officer of State AIDS Control Society for their help in completing the surveillance activities in a timely manner. I express my gratitude to all the State Referral Laboratories, National Referral Laboratories, State Surveillance Team members, Sentinel sites personnel and other National and International partners who helped us in completing the surveillance successfully.

Dr. Manoj V Murhekar

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Preface

Andhra Pradesh was considered once as a HIV high prevalent state in India. HIV Sentinel Surveillance (HSS) is the backbone of understanding the level and trend of HIV in the country. Initiated in 1998 under the leadership of NACO. APSACS's Strategic Information Management Unit (SIMU) Implemented 14th round of Surveillance among ANC clients in 2014-15.

The nationwide HIV Sentinel Surveillance (HSS) programme among antenatal clinic attendees (ANC) in India provides essential information on the dynamics of the HIV epidemic and helps to monitor trends and foresee the type of inputs needed to strengthen the prevention and control activities for different population groups and geographical regions. Andhra Pradesh State AIDS Control Society established under NACO has been collaborated with Regional Institute – NIE in the efforts of strengthening HIV/AIDS surveillance in Andhra Pradesh. The surveillance activities for all targeted groups have been scaled up in a phased manner and the network of sentinel sites has been expanded from a couple of sites in 1998, to 59 sites in 2014-15.

The overall HIV Prevalence among ANC population in 2014-15 continues to portray the concentrated epidemic nature in Andhra Pradesh Analysis of consistent sites shows that there was a downward trend of HIV prevalence among general population. Though the trend of HIV was declining in the state, the higher HIV prevalence among general population was persisting in certain districts of Andhra Pradesh.

I hope, the information provided in this report will be helpful to policy makers and stakeholders to focus their fight against the HIV/AIDS in right direction.

I thank all the sentinel sites, testing labs, SST Members, NIE and APSACS staff who contributed for this activity and also thank our participants who have given their serum samples for this surveillance.

I am confident that this report will help in shaping our various programmes and planning for appropriate strategy towards “Zero” HIV prevalence.

Dr. T. Geeta Pradhini, MBBS., DGO.,

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

Acquired immune deficiency syndrome or acquired immuno deficiency syndrome (AIDS) is a disease of the human immune system caused by the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). This condition progressively reduces the effectiveness of the immune system and leaves individuals susceptible to opportunistic infections. The first HIV infection was reported in the year 1981 in the United States of America. Afterwards the epidemic spread rapidly throughout the globe.

In India it was in 1986, the first HIV infection reported from Chennai, Tamil Nadu. In the last two decades the awful disease spread throughout the country.

Surveillance is a vital component of any disease control programme. The purpose of surveillance is to actually look for evidence of disease risk, to predict the pattern and to plan appropriate action for control and prevention. Providing meaningful insights for action at policy, strategy, planning, or implementation levels at the appropriate time is the key objective of surveillance. The HIV epidemic in India is concentrated, with high prevalence among high-risk groups, moderate prevalence among bridge populations, and low prevalence among general population. Unprotected sex with female sex workers (FSW), injecting drug users (IDU), and unprotected anal sex between men are the three primary routes of HIV transmission in India. HIV sentinel surveillance measures the prevalence of HIV in a specific risk group in a specific region at a specific point of time. The HIV sentinel surveillance system in India is based on the HIV transmission dynamics mentioned above and monitors the HIV epidemic patterns among the following groups:

1. High-risk groups

- a. Female sex workers
- b. Men who have sex with men (MSM)
- c. Injecting drug users
- d. People who are TG (transgender)/eunuchs

2. Bridge populations

- a. Single male migrants
- b. Long-distance Truckers (LDTs)
- c. People attending STI or gynaecology clinics (currently discontinued)

3. General population

a. Pregnant women attending the ANC clinics in urban and rural areas, and the ANC clinic attendees were considered proxy for general population. STI patients were considered proxy for people with high-risk behaviour (high-risk and bridge populations and their partners).

1.1. Objectives and Application of HIV Sentinel Surveillance

The key objectives of HIV sentinel surveillance in India are to:

1. Monitor trends in HIV prevalence over time.
2. Monitor the distribution and spread of HIV in different subgroups and geographical areas.
3. Identify emerging pockets of HIV epidemic in the country.
4. Applications of HIV sentinel surveillance data.
5. Estimate and project burden of HIV at state and national levels.
6. Support programme prioritization and resource allocation.
7. Assist evaluation of programme impact.
8. Provide evidence to advocacy efforts.

1.2. Evolution of HIV Sentinel Surveillance in India

HIV surveillance in India began in 1985 when the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) initiated a surveillance activity among blood donors and patients with STIs. After the National AIDS Control Organisation (NACO) was established in 1992, sentinel surveillance for HIV in India was initiated in 1993-94 with 52 sentinel sites in selected cities. In 1998, NACO formalized annual sentinel surveillance for HIV infection in the country with 180 sentinel sites, of which 176 were valid.

The first major expansion of the surveillance network was in 2003. More than 200 rural antenatal care (ANC) sentinel sites were established at the community health centre (CHC) level in most of the districts in high-prevalence states as well as some districts in low-prevalence states in North India. However, half of these ANC rural sites, especially those in low prevalence states of North India, were discontinued in the next round because they could not achieve the required target sample size due to poor utilization rates. Another significant expansion in 2003 was the addition of 30 FSW sites. Overall, 354 districts had at least one HSS site in 2003. From 2003 and until 2005, the same sentinel sites continued with expansion to 83 FSW and 30 injecting drug user (IDU) sites.

The year 2006 could be considered the watershed year for HSS development in India. The goal was to have at least one sentinel site in every district of India and new sentinel sites were added for all risk groups in that year. Key developments in 2006 included:

- ❖ Major expansion of STI and ANC urban sentinel sites in low-prevalence states of North India.
- ❖ Addition of rural ANC sites in high-prevalence states.
- ❖ Initiation of special ANC sites for 15-24-year-old pregnant women to monitor new infection.
- ❖ Expansion of sentinel sites among FSW, MSM and IDU.
- ❖ Initiation of sentinel sites among long-distance truckers (LDTs), single male migrants, and people who are transgenders (TG).
- ❖ Introduction of composite sites in HSS that facilitated establishment of sentinel sites in places where it had been difficult to do so, such as rural areas and places with fewer HRGs.

In year 2006, the scale of surveillance operations increased from 703 sites in high prevalence states in 2005 to 1,122 sites to cover the entire country. The surveillance also expanded from being only clinic-based to also include Targeted Intervention (TIs)

Six leading regional public health institutions in the country were involved to expand and strengthen the surveillance network and implementation activities and follow up programmes. These regional institutes (RI) provided technical support, guidance, monitoring, and supervision for implementing HSS. Two more RIs were created in 2008. Supervisory structures were further strengthened with constitution of central and state surveillance teams, which in comprised of public health experts, epidemiologists, and microbiologists from several medical colleges and research institutions.

During the subsequent three rounds of HSS (2007, 2008-09, and 2010-11), the focus was on expansion of surveillance among high-risk and bridge populations.

Key strategic HSS implementation improvements in these rounds included:

1. Technical validation of new sentinel sites by regional institutes before inclusion in surveillance and dropping poorly performing sites.

-
2. Introduced the dried blood spot (DBS) method of sample collection from high-risk groups (HRGs) to overcome logistic problems at HRG sites.
 3. Introduced informed consent at high-risk group sites to address ethical concerns.
 4. Initiated random sampling methods of recruitment at HRG sites, taking advantage of the availability of updated line lists of HRGs at the TI projects.
 5. Standardized training protocols across states with uniform session plans and materials, and adoption of a two-tier training plan with training-of-trainers (TOT) followed by training of site personnel.
 6. Developed a four-tier supervisory structure: national-level central team; regional institutes; state surveillance teams; and State AIDS Control Society (SACS) teams.
 7. Strengthened focus on supportive supervision and action-oriented monitoring.
 8. Increased focus on quality of planning, training, implementation, supervision and feedback.
 9. Decreased number of testing laboratories for ANC and STD samples, limiting them to high-performing laboratories with enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) facilities to ensure high-quality testing and close supervision.
 10. Developed a new web-based data management system to enhance data quality and ensure real time monitoring of surveillance activities.
 11. Initiated epidemiological investigation into unusual findings (sudden rise or decline in prevalence) to understand reasons and correct.
 12. Conducted pre-surveillance sentinel site evaluation to assess preparedness of site for HSS and to obtain profile-related information.

Between 2008 and 2009, the annual frequency of HSS was shifted to biennial (once in two years). STI sites were gradually being discontinued in 2008-09 and 2010-11. The 13th round of HSS was implemented at 763 sentinel sites (750 ANC and 13 STI sites). Most of the STI sites from the 12th round of HSS were phased out during HSS 2014-15. For high-risk and bridge populations, National Integrated Biological and Behavioural Surveillance (IBBS) was conducted to strengthen surveillance among these groups so HSS 2014-15 did not include high-risk groups.

CHAPTER 2:

Methodology and Implementation

This chapter describes HSS methodology and the implementation mechanisms adopted during HSS 2014-15.

2.1. Methodology of HIV Sentinel Surveillance at ANC Sentinel Sites

HIV sentinel surveillance is defined as a system of monitoring the HIV epidemic among the specified population groups by collecting information on HIV from designated sites (sentinel sites) over years, through a uniform and consistent methodology that allows comparison of findings across place and time, to guide programme response. A sentinel site is a designated service point/facility where blood specimens and relevant information are collected from a fixed number of eligible individuals from a specified population group over a fixed period of time, periodically, for the purpose of monitoring the HIV epidemic. Under HIV sentinel surveillance (HSS), recruitment of respondents is conducted for three months at selected ANC sentinel sites. Because of the low HIV prevalence in India, the classical survey method of sample size calculation that gives a large sample size cannot feasibly be collected through facility-based surveillance on an annual basis. Hence, a sample size of 400 for surveillance among ANC attendees was approved by a consensus of experts. Eligible respondents are enrolled until the sample size of 400 is reached or until the end of the surveillance period, whichever is earlier.

The eligibility criteria for recruiting respondents at an ANC sentinel sites were:

1. Age 15-49 years
2. Pregnant woman attending the antenatal clinic for the first time during the current round of surveillance period. “**Sampling method**” refers to the approach adopted at the sentinel sites for recruiting eligible individuals into HSS. Consecutive sampling method is adopted in HSS in India for ANC clinic attendees. After the start of surveillance, all individuals attending the ANC sentinel site facility who are eligible for inclusion are recruited in the order they attend the clinic. This sampling method removes all chances of selection or exclusion based on individual preferences or other reasons, and hence reduces the selection bias. It is convenient, feasible, and easy to follow.

“**Testing strategy**” refers to the approach adopted for collecting and testing blood specimens and handling the test results in HSS. In India, the unlinked anonymous

testing strategy is used. Testing is conducted on a portion of blood specimen collected for routine diagnostic purposes (such as syphilis) after removing all personal identifiers. Neither the information collected in the data form nor the HIV test result from the blood specimen is ever linked to the individual from whom the information/specimen is collected. Neither the personnel collecting the specimen nor the personnel testing the specimen are able to track the results back to the individual.

Hence, the personal identifiers such as name, address, outpatient registration number, etc. were not mentioned anywhere in the data form, blood specimen, or data form transportation or sample transportation sheets. Similarly, the HSS sample number or any mark indicating inclusion in HSS is not mentioned in the ANC register or patient/OPD card. The portion of the blood specimen with identifiers is used for reporting the results of the routine test for which it has been collected. The portion of the blood specimen without identifiers is sent for HIV testing under HSS.

“**Testing protocol**” refers to the number of HIV tests conducted on the blood specimen collected during HSS. A two-test protocol is adopted in HSS. The first test is of high sensitivity and second of high specificity and is confirmatory in nature. The second test is conducted only if the first is found to be positive. HIV testing under surveillance is for the purpose of ascertaining HIV levels and trends in a community and not for case diagnosis, which is why the two-test protocol is the global standard for surveillance.

The methodology of HSS at ANC sentinel sites is summarized in Table 1 below:

Sentinel site	Antenatal clinic
Sample size	400
Duration	3 months
Frequency	Once in 2 years (biennial)
Sampling method	Consecutive sampling
Eligibility	Pregnant women ages 15-49 years attending ANC clinic for the first time during the current round
Testing strategy	Unlinked anonymous testing
Blood specimen	Serum collected through venous blood specimen
Testing protocol	Two-test

2.2. Information Collected under HSS at ANC Sentinel Sites

HSS provides information on two bio-markers- HIV and syphilis. All blood specimens collected under HSS are tested for these two infections. When recruiting an individual in HSS, information is collected on basic demographic parameters such as age, education, occupation, spouse's occupation, and order of pregnancy. Collected information is kept minimal and restricted to those who might be asked under routine clinic procedures. During the recent rounds, a few questions were added to identify potential biases in the sample (e.g., source of referral) or to further profile the respondents with respect to their vulnerability (migration status of spouse) so that HIV prevalence estimates can be better explained and interpreted. HSS 2014-15 collects information on the following nine key demographic variables from every respondent.

1. Age: The age of the respondent is recorded in number of completed years. Since age is a part of eligibility criteria, improper recording or non-recording of age makes a sample invalid. Information on age helps identify the age groups with high HIV prevalence. In the absence of data on HIV incidence, high prevalence among younger age groups is considered a proxy for recent infections.

2. Literacy status: The literacy status of an individual has a direct bearing on the awareness levels with respect to risks of acquiring HIV and means of protecting oneself. Knowing the literacy status of the pregnant woman, helps in understanding the differentials in HIV prevalence and informs demographics about the women who are accessing services at ANC clinics. This information may also be helpful to compare and standardize the demographic profiles of two independent samples under HSS, while investigating any unusual increase or decrease in trends. Under HSS 2014-15, the literacy status of respondents was classified into five categories as defined below.

(a). Illiterate: People with no formal or non-formal education. **(b). Literate and till 5th standard:** People with non-formal education or those who joined school but did not study beyond 5th standard. **(c). 6th to 10th standard:** Those who studied beyond 5th standard but not beyond 10th standard. **(d). 11th to graduation:** Those who studied beyond 10th standard but not beyond graduation. Includes those with technical education/diplomas,. **(e). Post-graduation:** Those who studied beyond graduation.

3. Order of current pregnancy: The order of pregnancy denotes the number of times a woman has been pregnant. It includes the number of live births, still births,

and abortions. It is also referred to as gravidity. Women who are pregnant for the first time are referred to as *primi-gravida*. In the context of HIV, order of pregnancy indicates the duration of exposure to sexual risks. Since *primi-gravida* are likely to be exposed to sexual risks only recently, HIV prevalence among them is considered a proxy for new HIV infections and helps in understanding the HIV incidence in that region. The order of pregnancy is recorded as first, second, third, fourth or more.

4. Source of referral to the ANC clinic: Under HSS, ANC clinic attendees are asked who referred them to the clinic for antenatal check-up. This variable was added to the data collection form to understand the various sources of referral, especially to assess if there is any specific bias in the sample because of specific referrals of HIV-positive cases from any source. Published literature indicates that there is disproportionate referral of HIV-positive cases from private sector to government hospitals. Similarly, if there are higher numbers of referrals from ICTC/ ART centres in the sample, it may bias the HIV prevalence, as those respondents are likely to be people who have been exposed to HIV risk, to have HIV risk perception or who are known to be HIV-positive. This variable helps assess any such phenomenon. The response categories listed in the HSS data form include: (a). *Self-referral* (b). *Family/ relatives/ neighbours/ friends* (c). *NGO* (d). *Private hospital (doctors/ nurses)* (e). *Government hospital (including ANM/ ASHA)* (f). *ICTC/ ART centre*.

5. Current place of residence: HSS 2014-15 records the reported current residence of the respondent as 'Urban' or 'Rural'. If the current place of residence of the respondent i.e., the place she is living with her husband falls under Municipal Corporation, municipal council, or cantonment area, it is classified as 'urban'. Otherwise, it is recorded as 'rural'. Place of residence helps in studying the epidemic patterns in urban and rural areas separately and provides programmatic insight for implementing interventions. In the context of formerly high-prevalence states, urban-rural differentials of HIV prevalence is important because HIV is known to have spread to rural areas, sometimes with higher prevalence in these states. In low-prevalence states with rising HIV trends, migration from rural areas to high prevalence destinations is likely to play a role. Therefore, studying rural epidemics is important to characterise the epidemic appropriately.

6. Duration of stay at current place of residence: All the respondents were asked about the duration of stay at the current place of residence (the place she is living with her husband) and the responses are recorded in years and months. If the duration is less than one year, '0' years and the number of months as reported by

the respondent is recorded. If the duration is less than one month, the duration is recorded as '0' years, '1' month. Duration of stay at current place of residence is asked to ascertain whether the pregnant woman belongs to the place where the ANC clinic is situated. Because many pregnant women in India go to their maternal home for delivery, it is likely that they attend ANC clinic at their mother's place. If this is the case, her duration of stay will be only a few days or months. Although counsellors are instructed to ask where the respondent is living with her husband, this variable helps eliminate reporting errors. Also, it helps in understanding the duration of exposure to sexual risk. Similar to order of pregnancy, this variable also helps assess new HIV infections occurring in a region.

7. Current occupation of respondent: Certain occupations are associated with higher exposure and risk to HIV. It is important to understand the profile of respondents and differentials of HIV with respect to their occupation. For this purpose, HSS has categorized occupations into 13 categories ensuring that all the possible occupations are covered and the categories are relevant to the epidemiological analysis of HIV prevalence data. The occupation categories and their definitions were as follows: (a). Agricultural labourer (b). Non-agricultural labourer: includes workers at construction sites, quarries, stone crushers, road or canal works, brick-kilns. (c). Domestic servant (d). Skilled/semi-skilled worker: includes workers in small-scale or cottage industries; industrial/ factory workers; technicians such as electricians, masons, plumbers, carpenters, goldsmiths, iron-smiths, and those involved in automobile repair; artisans such as weavers, potters, painters, cobblers, shoe-makers, tailors. (e). Petty business/ small shop: includes vendors selling vegetables, fruits, milk, and newspapers; pan shop operators. (f). Large business/self-employed: includes professionals and business people. (g). Service (govt/pvt): those working on salary basis in government, private, or institutional sector; excludes drivers and hotel staff. (h). Student (i). Truck drivers/ helpers (j). Local transport workers (auto/ taxi drivers, handcart pullers, rickshaw pullers, etc.) (k). Hotel staff (l). Agricultural cultivators/ landholders (m). Housewife (in order to be consistent with the occupation codes for spouse of respondent, housewife is Code 14).

8. Current occupation of spouse: Occupation of spouse is an important epidemiological variable that may help identify population groups that are at higher risk of acquiring HIV. HSS used the same occupational categories as those used for the respondent. The two differences are that the category 'unemployed' (Code13) is used in the place of 'housewife' and there is an additional category: 'Not applicable (never married/widow/divorced/separated)' (Code 99).

9. Migration status of spouse: Analyses of drivers of the emerging epidemic in some low-prevalence states points to migration from these states to high-prevalence destinations (NACO Annual Report 2013-14, Chapter 2. Current Epidemiological Scenario of HIV/AIDS, pg.12). In order to assess the effects of migration status of spouse on HIV prevalence among ANC clinic attendees, respondents in HSS were asked whether spouse resides alone in another place/town away from wife for work for longer than 6 months. This question is not applicable to respondents who were never married/widowed/ divorced/separated.

2.3. Implementation Structure of HIV Sentinel Surveillance in India

HIV sentinel surveillance has a robust structure for planning, implementation, and review at national, regional, and state levels. The structure and key functions of involved agencies are shown in Figure 1.

National level: The National AIDS Control Organisation (NACO) is the nodal agency for strategy formulation and commissioning for each round of HSS. The Technical Resource Group on Surveillance and Estimation, comprised of experts from the fields of epidemiology, demography, surveillance, biostatistics, and laboratory services, advises NACO on the broad strategy and

Figure 1 : Implementing Structure of HIV Sentinel Surveillance in India

The main goal of implementing structure of HSS is for performing the assessment of the implementation plans of HSS and reviews the outcomes of each round. Two national institutes—National Institute of Health and Family Welfare (NIHFW) and ICMR-National Institute of Medical Statistics (ICMR-NIMS)—supports national level activity planning and coordination. In addition, the central team, which is coordinated by NIHFW, New Delhi and is comprised of experts from the Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), World Health Organisation (WHO), The Joint United Nations Programme on HIV and AIDS (UNAIDS), medical colleges, and other national and international agencies, provide support in training and supervision.

Regional level: Since 2006, NIE has been identified as regional institutes (RIs) for HSS to provide technical support to the State AIDS Control Societies (SACS) for all HSS activities in southern zone, starting with identification of new sites, training, monitoring and supervision, and improving quality of the data collection and their analysis. Data entry is another function performed by RIs. The team at each RI is comprised of two epidemiologists/public health experts and one micro-biologist, which are supported by one project coordinator, two research officers, one computer Assistant/data manager, and between four and ten data entry operators, depending on the volume of data entry. The names of the six regional institutes and the distribution of states among them are in Table 2.

State level: SACS is the primary agency responsible for implementation of HSS and NACO has appointed state epidemiologists at the SACS to support the activities and promote data analysis. In addition to these, every state has a surveillance team comprised of public health experts and microbiologists who support SACS in the training, supervision, and monitoring of the personnel involved in sentinel surveillance. State surveillance teams (SSTs) are formed by RIs in consultation with SACS. All activities are coordinated by RIs.

District level: In districts with functional district AIDS Prevention and Control Units (DAPCUs), the DAPCU staffs are involved in the coordination of HSS activities at the sentinel sites and the associated testing labs. Laboratory network Laboratory support is provided by a network of testing and reference labs. There are 117 state reference laboratories (SRLs) that conduct primary testing of blood specimens collected under HSS. Thirteen national reference laboratories (NRLs) provide external quality assurance to the SRLs through repeat testing of all HIV-positive blood specimens and 5% of HIV negative specimens.

Table 2: Regional Institutes for HIV Sentinel Surveillance and their State Allocation

Name of regional institution	Responsible states
Central Zone: All India Institute of Medical Science, New Delhi	Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Jharkhand, Uttaranchal, and Delhi.
North Zone: Post-graduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, Chandigarh	Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Punjab, and Chandigarh.
West Zone: National AIDS Research Institute, Pune	Maharashtra, Gujarat, Goa, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Daman & Diu, and Dadra Nagar Haveli.
South Zone: National Institute of Epidemiology, ICMR, Chennai	Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala, Odisha, Puducherry, and Lakshadweep and Telangana.
East Zone: National Institute of Cholera and Enteric Diseases, Kolkata	West Bengal, Chhattisgarh, Sikkim, Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Meghalaya, and Nagaland.
Northeast Zone: Regional Institute of Medical Sciences, Imphal	Manipur, Mizoram, Tripura, Assam, and Arunachal Pradesh.

2.4. Key Initiatives during HIV Sentinel Surveillance 2014-15:

In response to key issues identified in the implementation of HSS during the previous rounds and to improve the quality and timeliness of the surveillance process in the 14th round, several new initiatives were implemented as part of continuous quality improvement.

SACS checklist for preparatory activities:

This was developed to monitor the planning process for HSS in each state (Annex 3). All the preparatory activities were broken into specific tasks with clear timelines and SACS were required to submit the completion status for each task. A team of officers from NACO coordinated with state nodal persons to ensure that preparatory activities in all states adhered to the timelines.

Pre-surveillance sentinel site evaluation (SSE):

A pre-surveillance evaluation of ANC and STD sentinel sites was conducted to identify and correct human resources and infrastructure-related issues at the sentinel sites before initiation of surveillance. The evaluation also provided site information such as type of facility, average OPD attendance, availability of HIV and AIDS services, and distance of facilities from HSS labs (Annex 4), which may have implications on adherence to methodology.

Standard operational manuals, wall charts, and bilingual data forms:

These were developed to simplify the HSS methodology for site-level personnel and to ensure uniform implementation of the guidelines in all the sentinel sites. These were printed centrally and distributed across the country.

Training during HSS 2014-15:

Steps to improve quality of training:

1. A well-structured training programme was adopted to ensure that all the personnel involved in HSS at different levels were adequately and uniformly trained in the respective areas of responsibility.
2. The training agenda, curriculum, and planning and reporting formats were standardized and used in all the states. Standard slide sets and training manuals for training of sentinel site personnel were developed centrally to ensure uniformity.
3. Trainings included group work and a “know your sentinel site” exercise, which helped participants identify the routine practices that could affect the implementation of surveillance at their sites and recommended actions to address the same.
4. Pre and post-test assessments were given to each participant at the site-level trainings. Analysis of these scores helped state teams to identify the priority sites for supervisory visits.
5. Training reports for each batch were submitted in standard formats at the end of the each training.

Details of trainings:

1. Trainings started with two batches of national pre-surveillance meetings with about 90 personnel from regional institutes and SACS to discuss the critical aspects of planning for HSS 2014-15 and to clearly understand the system for supportive supervision through the online Strategic Information Management System (SIMS) application.
2. This was followed by 2-day regional TOTs organised by the RIs for SACS officers and state surveillance teams, comprised of public health experts and microbiologists, to create state-level master trainers and to plan for the site-level trainings.
3. Site-level trainings (2 days per batch @ 8-10 sites per batch) were conducted in all the states. Representatives from the regional institutes and NACO observed the trainings to ensure that trainings were provided as per the protocol and that all the sessions were covered as per the session plan.
4. Separate trainings on surveillance testing protocols and lab reporting mechanisms through the SIMS application for HSS were organised for microbiologists and lab technicians from 117 ANC/STD testing labs and 13 NRLs.
5. Overall, 40 central team members; 30 officers from six RIs; 95 SACS officers including in-charge surveillance, Epidemiologists, and M&E officers; 280 state surveillance team members; 260 laboratory personnel including microbiologists and lab technicians from the designated testing labs; and more than 3,000 sentinel site personnel including medical officers, nurse/counsellors, and lab technicians were trained under HSS 2014-15.

Laboratory system: For HSS 2014-15, the laboratory system was strengthened by limiting the testing of specimens to designated SRLs. Real-time monitoring of the quality of blood specimens and laboratory processes was achieved through introduction of web based reporting through the SIMS application for HSS. Efforts were made to standardize quality assurance aspects of sample testing under HSS and to streamline responses in case of discordant test results between testing lab and reference lab through the SIMS application.

Supervisory mechanisms for HSS 2014-15: Supervision of all HSS activities was prioritized to ensure smooth implementation and high-quality data collection. Extensive mechanisms were developed to set up a comprehensive supervisory system

for HSS and to ensure that 100% of HSS sites were visited in the first 15 days of the start of sample collection. The principles adopted included action-oriented supervision, real-time monitoring and feedback, accountability for providing feedback and taking action, and an integrated web-based system to enhance the reach and effectiveness of supervision.

SIMS modules for web-based supervision.

Specific modules were developed and made operational in the web-based SIMS for HSS to facilitate real-time monitoring of HSS 2014-15.

1. Field supervision was conducted by trained supervisors who visited the sentinel sites to monitor the quality of recruitment of respondents and other site-level procedures. Real-time reporting of field supervision used the SIMS supervisor module via the field supervisory quick feedback and action taken report sub-modules. The module was used extensively by all the supervisors and helped in quick identification and resolution of challenges in the field.
2. Data were supervised by data managers at RIs to monitor the quality of data collection and transportation using the SIMS module.
3. Laboratory supervision was conducted by SRLs and NRLs to monitor the quality of blood specimens, progress in laboratory processing, and external quality assurance, using the SIMS lab module.

Overall, 80% of supervisors reported on the SIMS field supervisor quick feedback format, and 52% of action taken report formats were submitted by HSS focal persons from SACS and RIs. Laboratory reporting through the lab module was completed by 87% of SRLs.

Integrated monitoring and supervision plan

1. An integrated supervision plan for each state was developed by RIs, SACS, and NIHFWS to avoid duplication in monitoring coverage, thereby facilitating maximum coverage of surveillance sites.
2. The first round of visits was conducted by RI, SACS, and SST members. Central team members (CTM) visited the top priority sites identified in feedback from the first round of visits. Subsequent visits were based on priority with a goal of making at least three visits to each identified site which require supervision.

SMS-based daily reporting from sentinel sites

This was piloted in last round and implemented in this round as an approach of daily reporting of the number of samples collected at each sentinel site through a group SMS from a registered mobile number to a central server. The system automatically compiled and displayed site-wise data on an Excel format on a real-time basis. Access to this web-based application was given to SACS, RIs, and DAC and facilitated identification of sites with poor performance and enabled initiation of corrective action at sites that initiated HSS late; where sample collection was too slow or too fast; and where there were large gaps in sample collection.

CHAPTER 3.

Profile of Respondents

The HIV epidemic has been one of the most challenging modern public health problems for India. Provisional estimates in the year 2015 the number of people living with HIV in India at 25 lakhs while in Andhra Pradesh the provisional estimates showed that PLHAs at 3 lakhs. The Chapter-3 deals with the profile of respondents of HIV surveillance survey 2014-15 of Andhra Pradesh.

Review of the profile of the respondents showed that, at state level, three-fourth of respondents (75.6%) were in the age group of 15-24 years, the remaining 24.4% respondents fall in the age group of 25 to 44 years group and in the age group of 45-49 years no one has got registered.

The total literacy of the respondents showed 83.4%; among them 39.5% respondents fall in the literacy level of 6th to 10th standard followed by 22% literates studied up to 5th standard. 11th to graduates accounted for 19.4% while 2.5% were post graduates.

Around 90% of the ANC attendees (47.9% and 41.7% respectively) were in the first and second pregnancy. The order of current pregnancy for third recorded at 8.7% and fourth and more was recorded as 1.6%.

More than 71.1% of the respondents reported that their current place of resident was rural and the remaining 28.9% responded that their place of residence was urban.

Around 74% of ANC Clinic attendees reported that they were housewives followed by about 17% were agricultural labourers. Non-agricultural labourers were reported at 2.8% while people in service reported at 2.5%. The remaining respondent's occupation reported were around one and less than one percent. When it comes to the occupation of profile of the spouses, it was reported that around 32% were agricultural labourers followed by 18.2% were non agricultural labourers. Skilled and semi skilled workers reported at 13.8% followed by 13.7% of the spouses belonged to the category of service.

Of the total 15095 ANC Attendees, only 0.3% (50) reported as HIV Positive and in case of Syphilis, only 0.1% (15) reported as positive.

Table 3: Profile of Respondents at State Level, HSS 2014-15

Background characteristics	Number	%
Age (N=15095)		
15-24	11409	75.6
25-34	3605	23.9
35-44	81	0.5
45-49	0	0.0
Literacy status (N=15041)		
Illiterate	2499	16.6
Literate and till 5th standard	3311	22.0
6th to 10th standard	5947	39.5
11th to Graduation	2913	19.4
Post Graduation	371	2.5
Order of current pregnancy (N=15015)		
First	7192	47.9
Second	6268	41.7
Third	1308	8.7
Fourth or more	247	1.6
Source of referral pregnancy (N=15082)		
Self referral	2627	17.4
Family/Relatives/Neighbors/Friends	4112	27.4
NGO	63	0.4
Private Hospital	647	4.3
Govt. Hospital	7616	50.7
ICTC/ART Centre	17	0.1
Current place of residence (N=15007)		
Urban	4344	28.9
Rural	10663	71.1
Current occupation of the respondent (N=15053)		
Agricultural Labourer	2539	16.9
Non-Agricultural labourer	418	2.8
Domestic servant	26	0.2
Skilled/Semiskilled worker	188	1.2
Petty business	51	0.3
Large business/self employed	31	0.2

Service (Govt./Pvt.)	379	2.5
Student	62	0.4
Truck driver/helper	2	0.0
Local transport worker	1	0.0
Hotel staff	26	0.2
Agricultural cultivator/landholder	208	1.4
Housewife	11122	73.9
Current occupation of the spouse (N=15074)		
Agricultural Labourer	4804	31.9
Non-Agricultural labourer	2747	18.2
Domestic servant	17	0.1
Skilled/Semiskilled worker	2076	13.8
Petty business	697	4.6
Large business/self employed	340	2.3
Service (Govt./Pvt.)	2061	13.7
Student	26	0.2
Truck driver/helper	374	2.5
Local transport worker	1111	7.4
Hotel staff	97	0.6
Agricultural cultivator/landholder	676	4.5
Unemployed	43	0.3
Not Applicable	5	0.0
Spouse resides alone in another place/town from wife for work for longer than 6 months (N=14993)		
Yes	309	2.1
No	14673	97.9
99	11	0.1
HIV (N=15095)		
Negative	15045	99.7
Positive	50	0.3
Syph (N=15095)		
Negative	15080	99.9
Positive	15	0.1

3.1. Age

HIV sentinel surveillance survey was conducted on 15095 ANCs and the Age in completed years is recorded for all the respondent. A majority of 75.6% fall in the age group of 15-24 years followed by 24% belong to the age group of 25-34 years. Only 0.5% is recorded for the age group of 35-44 and no one has registered in the age group of 45-49.

Figure 2: Percent Distribution of respondents by age group in Andhra Pradesh, HSS, 2014-15

The District wise respondents are given in the following table 4. The proportion of respondents in the age group of 15-24 years varied from 56.8% in Ananthapur to 84.4% in West Godhavari. Besides Prakasam(84.3%), the districts of Guntur (83.6%), Vizianagaram (83.5%), Krishna (82.0%), East Godavari (81.4%), and Nellore (77.6%), Kurnool (75.3), Srikakulam (70.3). The districts Visakhapatnam (69.8), Chittoor (67.4), and Cuddapah(62.4), had over 60% of respondents in the 15-24 years of age group. The proportion of respondents in the age group of 25-34 years varied from 15.3% in West Godhavari to 42.2% in Anantapur District. Besides Cuddapah (36.5%), Chittoor (31.4%) and Srikakulam and Visakhapatnam (29.7%), Kurnool (24.2), Nellore(21.8), East Godhavari (18.4) Krishna (17.4), Guntur (16.3), Vizianagaram (16.2) and Prakasam(15.4), had over 38% of respondents in 25-34 years of age group showed more than 50% of respondents in the young age group. Less than 2% of the respondents in the districts of the state belonged to this age group (35-44 years). And there were no respondents in the age group of 45-49 years.

Table 4: Percent Distribution of respondents by age group and district, HSS 2014-15

	15-24	25-34	35-44	45-49	N
	%	%	%	%	
Anantapur	56.8	42.2	1.0	0.0	1195
Chittoor	67.4	31.4	1.2	0.0	1199
Cuddapah	62.4	36.5	1.1	0.0	800
East Godavari	81.4	18.4	0.3	0.0	1144
Guntur	83.6	16.3	0.2	0.0	1200
Krishna	82.0	17.4	0.6	0.0	1194
Kurnool	75.3	24.2	0.5	0.0	1200
Nellore	77.6	21.8	0.7	0.0	1200
Prakasam	84.3	15.4	0.3	0.0	1166
Srikakulam	70.3	29.7	0.0	0.0	799
Visakhapatnam	69.8	29.7	0.5	0.0	1600
Vizianagaram	83.5	16.2	0.3	0.0	1200
West Godavari	84.4	15.3	0.3	0.0	1198

3.2. Literacy Status

Under HSS 2014-15, respondent's literacy status were classified into five categories:

1. Illiterate: people with no formal or non-formal education.
2. Literate and till 5th standard: people with non-formal education or those who joined school but had not studied beyond 5th standard.
3. 6th to 10th standard: people who studied beyond 5th standard but not beyond 10th standard.
4. 11th to graduation: people who studied beyond 10th standard but not beyond graduation. Includes those with technical education/diplomas.
5. Post-graduation: people who studied beyond graduation.

More than 16% of respondents at the state level had no formal education. Around 22.02% of respondents studied up to fifth standard and the highest proportion of respondents (39.53%) studied between sixth and tenth standards. Around 19.37% of the respondents reported to have studied beyond 10th standard and up to graduation, while another about 2.47% had studied beyond graduation.

Figure 3: Percent Distribution of respondents by education in Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

The proportion of illiterates varied from 6.7% in East Godavari to 30.3% in Kurnool. Prakasam (25.2%), Vizianagaram (24.4%), Guntur (21.9%), Cuddapah (19.3%), Nellore (18.2%), Anantapur (18%), Chittoor and Visakhapatnam (11.1%), Srikakulam (10.6%) West Godavari (10.5%) and Krishna (9.1%) respondents who were illiterates.

Table 5: Percent Distribution of respondents by education in Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

	Illiterate	Literate and till 5th standard	6th to 10th standard	11th to Graduation	Post Graduation	N
	%	%	%	%	%	
Anantapur	18.0	31.4	34.6	11.4	4.6	1177
Chittoor	11.1	10.1	47.3	27.6	3.9	1194
Cuddapah	19.3	47.8	20.8	11.6	0.6	800
East Godavari	6.7	15.0	59.6	18.1	0.7	1140
Guntur	21.9	18.7	40.8	16.8	1.8	1198
Krishna	9.1	10.6	49.3	26.2	4.8	1194
Kurnool	30.3	28.2	29.7	10.9	0.8	1197
Nellore	18.2	29.3	39.9	11.9	0.7	1196
Prakasam	25.2	27.3	34.2	11.9	1.5	1162
Srikakulam	10.6	27.4	37.5	23.8	0.8	795
Visakhapatnam	11.1	11.2	37.0	34.7	6.1	1595
Vizianagaram	24.4	16.6	35.6	22.4	1.0	1200
West Godavari	10.5	26.6	42.5	18.0	2.4	1193

3.3. Order of Pregnancy

The order of pregnancy denotes the number of times a woman has become pregnant. It includes the number of live births, still births, and abortions. It is also referred to as 'gravidity'. As noted earlier, in the context of HIV, order of pregnancy indicates the duration of exposure to sexual risks, so HIV prevalence among primi-gravida is considered a proxy for new HIV infections and is an indicator of state HIV incidence.

At the state level, a little less than half (48%) of the respondents reported being pregnant for the first time (primi-gravida), while close to 42% were pregnant for the second time, and 9% of respondents reported that it was their third pregnancy. Around 2% of respondents were pregnant for the fourth or more time (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Percent Distribution of respondents by Order of Pregnancy in Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

At the district level, the percentage of primi-gravida varied between 33.3% in Cuddapah to 60.2% in Srikakulam. Vizianagaram (54.8%), West Godavari (54.4%), Krishna (53.6%) and East Godavari (51.4%) also had higher percent of primi-gravida among respondents. On the other hand, Cuddapah (53.6%), Nellore (48.1%) and Prakasam (44.1%) had higher percent of respondents who were pregnant for second time (Table 6). Those who were pregnant for third time varied between 3.4% in Srikakulam to 15.4% in Kurnool. And those who were pregnant for fourth or more time pregnancy between 0.2% in Vizianagaram to 4.6% in Kurnool District.

Table 6: Percent Distribution of respondents by Order of Pregnancy in the districts of Andhra Pradesh state, HSS 2014-15

	First	Second	Third	Fourth or more	N
	%	%	%	%	
Anantapur	46.8	42.7	8.4	2.1	1172
Chittoor	45.4	41.2	11.5	1.9	1187
Cuddapah	33.3	53.6	11.7	1.4	796
East Godavari	51.4	41.3	6.2	1.1	1142
Guntur	46.0	41.9	10.5	1.5	1197
Krishna	53.6	39.5	6.2	0.8	1191
Kurnool	44.9	35.1	15.4	4.6	1198

Nellore	38.2	48.1	12.3	1.4	1194
Prakasam	42.4	44.1	10.2	3.2	1162
Srikakulam	60.2	36.0	3.4	0.5	798
Visakhapatnam	49.8	41.4	7.0	1.8	1595
Vizianagaram	54.8	41.4	3.7	0.2	1198
West Godavari	54.4	38.5	6.5	0.6	1185

3.4 Source of Referral to the ANC Clinic

This variable illuminates the various sources of referral, and helps identify if a specific bias is being introduced in the sample due to specific referrals of HIV-positive cases from any source. The response categories listed in the HSS data form include self-referral; family/relative/ neighbour/friend; NGO; private hospital (doctor/nurse); government hospital (including ANM/ASHA); and ICTC/ ART centre. Government health care providers doctors/nurses at PHC, and CHC.

Government hospital is the major source of referral to ANC clinics, accounting for 50.7% of respondents, followed by family/relative/neighbour/friend (27.4%), and self referral (17.43%). Private Hospitals referral 4.30%, NGOs centres accounted for 0.42%. Only 0.11% had been referred by ICTC/ART Centres at the state level.

Figure 5: Percent Distribution of respondents by source of referral in Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

Referral from government service providers was higher in the district of Vizianagaram (87.8%), Srikakulam (86.1%), Cuddapah (77.8%), and West Godavari (77%). There were less referral from the government facilities in Prakasam (25.2%) and it was low in East Godavari (18.4%), In Prakasam 64.2% of ANC clinic attendees came of their own accord, i.e., were not referred. This was followed by the districts of Anantapur (51.7%), Self-referrals were lowest in the districts of Srikakulam (4.1%), and Vizianagaram (2.9%).

While overall private sector referrals accounted for around 4.30% of respondents, Chittoor (28.4%) had higher proportions of private sector referrals. While NGOs accounted for only 0.42% of all respondents as a source of referral to ANC clinics, the districts of Ananthapur (2.7%) and Nellore (1.2%) showed relatively higher levels of NGO referrals. The proportion of referral from ICTC/ART centres was also low (0.11%), however, it was shown only one District Nellore (1.4%) showed relatively higher proportions of referrals from ICTC/ART centres and all other districts shown as 0% (Table 7).

Table 7: Percent Distribution of respondents by source of referral and district, HSS 2014-15

	Self referral	Family/Relatives/Neighbors/Friends	NGO	Private Hospital	Govt. Hospital	ICTC/ART Centre	
District	%	%	%	%	%	%	N
Anantapur	51.7	0.1	2.7	0.1	45.4	0.0	1193
Chittoor	15.9	4.9	0.4	28.4	50.4	0.0	1198
Cuddapah	7.8	8.1	0.1	6.1	77.8	0.0	799
East Godavari	12.2	69.0	0.2	0.3	18.4	0.0	1144
Guntur	6.7	59.5	0.0	0.2	33.7	0.0	1199
Krishna	13.3	53.4	0.0	0.0	33.2	0.0	1194
Kurnool	5.9	34.0	0.0	2.2	57.9	0.0	1200
Nellore	12.8	42.3	1.2	2.2	40.2	1.4	1199
Prakasam	64.2	9.9	0.8	0.0	25.2	0.0	1164
Srikakulam	4.1	9.6	0.0	0.1	86.1	0.0	799
Visakhapatnam	15.1	28.5	0.0	12.4	44.1	0.0	1598
Vizianagaram	2.9	9.3	0.0	0.0	87.8	0.0	1200
West Godavari	8.4	14.6	0.0	0.1	77.0	0.0	1195

3.5. Current Place of Residence

2014-15 records the reported current residence of the respondent as urban or rural. If the current place of residence of the respondent was Municipal Corporation, municipal council, or cantonment area, it was classified as urban. Otherwise, it was recorded as rural.

Figure 6: Percent Distribution of respondents by Current Place of residence in Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15.

At the state level, 71% of respondents reported to be currently residing in rural areas and the rest (29%) reported to be currently residing in urban areas. At the district level, the% of urban varied between 6% in Srikakulam to 39% in Chittoor, followed by Cuddapah(38%), Anantapur (37.6%), Visakhapatnam (36.8%), Krishna(34.9%) Prakasam(33.6%) and Kurnool(30.8%) of respondents residing in urban areas. On the other hand, the districts currently residing in rural varied between 61% in Chittoor to 94% in Srikakulam. Followed by East Godavari (85.1%), Vizianagarm (79.2%), Guntur (78.1%), West godavar(73.6%) and Nellore (72.3%) who reported rural area as their residence (Table 8).

Table 8: Percent Distribution of respondents by Current Place of residence and district, HSS 2014-15

District	Urban	Rural	N
Anantapur	37.6	62.4	1177
Chittoor	39.0	61.0	1190
Cuddapah	38.0	62.0	799
East Godavari	14.9	85.1	1138
Guntur	21.9	78.1	1194
Krishna	34.9	65.1	1192
Kurnool	30.8	69.2	1199
Nellore	27.7	72.3	1194
Prakasam	33.6	66.4	1154
Srikakulam	6.0	94.0	794
Visakhapatnam	36.8	63.2	1596
Vizianagaram	20.8	79.2	1198
West Godavari	26.4	73.6	1182

3.6. Current Occupation of the Respondent

Certain occupations are associated with higher exposure and risk to HIV. It is important to understand the profile of respondents with respect to their occupation. For this purpose, HSS has categorized 13 occupations, as detailed in an earlier chapter.

Figure 7: Percent Distribution of respondents by Occupation in Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

At the state level, the majority of the respondents (74%) were housewives, and 16.9% of respondents reported to have engaged in Agricultural labourers and non-agricultural labourers (2.8%), Service (Govt./Pvt.) were accounted for 2.5%, Skilled/Semi-skilled work was (1.2%), and followed by Agricultural cultivator/landholder respondents (1.4%), Petty business (0.3%), Student respondents (0.4%), Hotel staff and Large business/self employed (0.2%), Very low percent of respondents were Truck driver/helper 0.02% and Local transport worker respondents were 0.01%.

In all the districts, majority of respondents were housewives. Except Kurnool (55.1%), Visakhapatnam (64%) and Guntur (64.3%), all districts had over 64% of respondents who were housewives. Following housewife, a high proportion of respondents reported that their occupation as agricultural labourers in the districts of Guntur (25.8%), West Godavari (24.6%), Nellore (23.9%), Kurnool (22.8%), Visakhapatnam (22.5%), Vizianagaram (21.8%) and Prakasam (21%). Similarly, a higher proportion of respondents reported being in non-agricultural labourers in the districts of Srikakulam (11.3%), and Cuddapah (6.3%). In Visakhapatnam (9.5%), Nellore (3.3%), Guntur and Krishna above 2% of respondents reported to be Service (Govt./Pvt.).

Table 9: Percent Distribution of respondents by Occupation in the districts of Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

	Agricultural Labourer	Non-Agricultural labourer	Domestic servant	Skilled/Semiskilled worker	Petty business	Large business/self employed	Service (Govt./Pvt.)	Student	Truck driver/helper	Local transport worker	Hotel staff	Agricultural cultivator/landholder	Housewife	N
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	N
Anantapur	14.0	1.5	0.1	0.9	0.2	1.2	1.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	1.5	0.9	78.3	1170
Chittoor	1.8	0.5	0.0	0.3	0.3	0.0	1.4	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	95.6	1195
Cuddapah	15.1	6.3	0.0	6.4	1.1	0.8	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	68.9	800
East Godavari	4.1	2.3	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.1	1.6	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.1	1.1	89.4	1143
Guntur	25.8	3.7	0.6	1.8	0.3	0.0	2.4	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.5	64.3	1200
Krishna	1.6	0.6	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.2	2.2	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	94.9	1193
Kurnool	22.8	3.0	0.1	3.7	0.7	0.0	1.9	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.1	12.3	55.1	1200
Nellore	23.9	3.8	0.4	1.3	0.9	0.0	3.3	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	65.8	1199
Prakasam	21.0	3.5	0.8	0.7	0.3	0.3	0.9	0.4	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	71.8	1164
Srikakulam	17.3	11.3	0.0	0.1	0.3	0.0	1.0	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	69.5	799
Visakhapatnam	22.5	1.1	0.1	0.6	0.6	0.3	9.5	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	64.0	1593
Vizianagaram	21.8	2.0	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.0	1.6	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.2	1.8	71.9	1200
West Godavari	24.6	1.1	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	72.1	1197

3.7. Current Occupation of Spouse

The respondents were also asked about the current occupation of their spouses. The “occupation of spouse” is an important epidemiological variable that may help to identify population groups and their higher risk of acquiring HIV. HSS used the same occupational categories as those used for the respondent. The two differences were that the category ‘unemployed’ (Code 13) is used in the place of ‘housewife’ and there is an additional category ‘not applicable’ (for never married/widowed/divorced/separated)’ (Code 99).

Figure 8: Percent Distribution of respondents by the Occupation of spouse in Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

At the state level, Agricultural labourers (32%), non-agricultural labourers (18.2%), skilled/ semi- skilled workers (13.8%), service (govt/pvt) (13.7%), Local transport workers (7.4%), agricultural cultivators/landlords and petty business are above 4.5% and Truck driver/helpers and Large business/self employed are above 2%, Hotel staff (0.6%), unemployees (0.3%) and Students (0.2%). Only 0.1% of respondents reported that their spouse was a Domestic servant. Similar patterns were noted across the states with certain inter-state variations.

Table 10: Percent Distribution of respondents by the Occupation of spouse and district, HSS 2014-15

	Agricultural Labourer	Non-Agricultural labourer	Domestic servant	Skilled/Semiskilled worker	Petty business	Large business/self employed	Service (Govt./Pvt.)	Student	Truck driver/helper	Local transport worker	Hotel staff	Agricultural cultivator/landholder	Unemployed	Not Applicable	N
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	
Anantapur	44.7	15.5	0.1	9.5	3.2	3.5	7.8	0.1	3.0	6.1	1.7	4.4	0.3	0.1	1190
Chittoor	17.9	11.9	0.2	22.2	9.0	2.3	14.0	0.2	5.8	8.0	0.5	8.2	0.0	0.0	1193
Cuddapah	18.9	23.2	0.0	8.1	3.1	7.9	7.3	0.5	4.0	17.0	0.1	9.9	0.0	0.0	799
East Godavari	45.6	11.1	0.1	18.6	4.6	0.3	9.6	0.1	2.3	5.2	0.5	1.6	0.2	0.1	1143
Guntur	30.4	22.4	0.1	17.4	4.2	0.5	12.8	0.3	1.3	7.8	0.7	1.7	0.5	0.0	1199
Krishna	37.2	5.9	0.0	19.4	6.1	3.1	18.3	0.3	0.9	8.0	0.4	0.3	0.0	0.0	1194
Kurnool	18.4	15.0	0.2	17.9	4.0	1.3	9.7	0.2	3.7	7.3	0.3	22.1	0.0	0.0	1197
Nellore	28.7	26.0	0.2	12.2	5.7	2.3	10.1	0.2	1.8	9.9	0.9	1.9	0.2	0.0	1197
Prakasam	31.6	27.3	0.6	11.3	3.4	2.4	9.7	0.2	2.1	8.8	1.2	0.7	0.5	0.1	1166
Srikakulam	38.8	25.0	0.0	7.1	4.4	1.3	16.4	0.0	1.1	5.4	0.1	0.4	0.0	0.0	799
Visakhapatnam	22.4	21.5	0.1	8.2	5.9	3.1	29.6	0.3	2.4	4.9	0.3	0.1	1.1	0.1	1600
Vizianagaram	28.1	14.4	0.0	15.4	4.4	0.8	19.8	0.1	1.9	6.0	1.2	7.5	0.4	0.0	1200
West Godavari	53.5	20.2	0.0	9.5	1.1	1.7	5.8	0.0	2.0	4.7	0.3	1.2	0.1	0.0	1197

3.8. Migration Status of Spouse

In order to assess the relationship between spousal migration status and HIV prevalence among ANC clinic attendees, respondents in HSS were asked whether spouse resides in another place/town away from wife for work for longer than 6 months. This question was not applicable to those respondents who were never married/widowed/divorced/separated.

Figure 9: Percentage of respondents with Migrant spouse in Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

At the state level, around 2% of respondents reported that their spouses were migrants, though there were significant inter-district variations. The highest proportion of respondents with a migrant spouse was Anantapur (5.9%), followed by other districts of Chittoor (5.7%), Kurnool (3%), Prakasam (2.7%), and Cuddapah (2.4%) were showed higher proportions of respondents with a migrant spouse (Table 11).

Table 11: Percentage of respondents with Migrant spouse and district, HSS 2014-15

District	% respondents with migrant spouse	N
Anantapur	5.9	1173
Chittoor	5.7	1192
Cuddapah	2.4	793
East Godavari	1.1	1134
Guntur	1.3	1197
Krishna	0.5	1189
Kurnool	3.0	1193
Nellore	1.3	1192
Prakasam	2.7	1164
Srikakulam	0.5	795
Visakhapatnam	0.3	1595
Vizianagaram	1.8	1199
West Godavari	0.5	1177

CHAPTER 4.

Levels of HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees

HIV prevalence is the proportion of respondents who are found HIV positive at a given point of time in a specified geographic area. It indicates the burden of the epidemic in different population groups.

HIV prevalence among ANC clinic attendees is considered as proxy for HIV burden in general population. HIV prevalence of 1% or more among ANC clinic attendees is considered as high level, 0.5-0.99% is considered as moderate level and less than 0.5% is considered as low HIV prevalence for the analysis purpose in this report. This chapter describes the levels of HIV prevalence among ANC clinic attendees at state and district level.

4.1. HIV Prevalence at State and District Level

Figure 10: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by district, HSS 2014-15

Table 12: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees in the state of Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

District	HIV Prevalence (%)
Kadapa	0.63
Prakasam	0.51
West Godavari	0.50

Srikakulam	0.50
Visakhapatnam	0.44
Guntur	0.42
Andhra Pradesh	0.35
East Godavari	0.35
Nellore	0.25
Anantapur	0.25
Chittoor	0.17
Kurnool	0.17
Vizianagaram	0.17
Krishna	0.08

4.2. Variations in the Number of High HIV-Prevalence Sites over Time

Within the state there were variations in HIV prevalence among the sites as well as the districts. There were 13 sites showing HIV prevalence as 'zero'.

Table 13:	
No. of sites with ANC HIV prevalence of 1% or more	3
No. of sites with ANC HIV prevalence of less than 1%	22
No. of sites with ANC HIV prevalence of zero	13
Total	38

CHAPTER 5.

HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Background Characteristics

As noted in the previous chapter, the HIV epidemic in India is a concentrated epidemic with heterogeneous distribution across the various states and districts. While HIV prevalence among ANC clinic attendees reflected the epidemic patterns in the general population, this chapter provides a detailed analysis of the differentials in prevalence by various background characteristics of ANC clinic attendees to increase understanding of sub- groups that are more likely to be at risk of HIV infection. This information allows programme planners to design and prioritize interventions that are most needed. As discussed in Chapter 3, HSS 2014-15 collected information on the following nine key demographic variables from every respondent.

1. Age
2. Literacy status
3. Order of current pregnancy
4. Source of referral to the ANC clinic
5. Current place of residence
6. Duration of stay at current place of residence
7. Current occupation of respondent
8. Current occupation of spouse
9. Migration status of spouse

the following sections present the findings for each of these background characteristics.

5.1. HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Age :

Age-specific HIV prevalence data from HSS 2014-15 showed that HIV prevalence was higher among the 35-44 age group of the respondents (Figure 11). ANC clinic attendees in the younger age group (15-24 years) had a HIV prevalence of 0.27%, while it was 0.47% among those aged 25-34 years.

Figure 11: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Age

The District wise HIV prevalence among ANC clinic attendees by age are shown in the table 14. The Prevalence in the age group of 15-24 years varied from 0.00% in Srikakulam to 0.60% in Kadapa/Cuddapah District. The other Districts prevalence rates as are shown in the table below. The prevalence in the age group of 25-49 years varied from 0.00% in Krishna and Chittoor to 1.69% in Srikakulam District followed by 1.64% in Prakasam District.

Table 14: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Age and District, HSS 2014-15				
	15-24		25-49	
Andhra Pradesh	0.27	11409	0.52	3686
Anantapur	0.15	679	0.39	516
Chittoor	0.25	808	0.00	391
Cuddapah	0.60	499	0.66	301
East Godavari	0.32	931	0.47	213
Guntur	0.40	1003	0.51	197
Krishna	0.10	979	0.00	215
Kurnool	0.11	904	0.34	296
Nellore	0.32	931	0.00	269
Prakasam	0.31	983	1.64	183
Srikakulam	0.00	562	1.69	237
Visakhapatnam	0.36	1117	0.62	483
Vizianagaram	0.10	1002	0.51	198
West Godavari	0.49	1011	0.53	187

5.2. HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Literacy Status

Figure 12: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees in Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

The District-wise HIV prevalence among ANC clinic attendees by Literacy Status were shown in the following table 15. The Prevalence in the Literacy Status group of Illiterate varied from 0% in Chittoor, Srikakulam, Krishna and East Godavari to 1.7% in Visakhapatnam District followed by West Godavari 1.6% and Cuddapah 1.3%. The prevalence in the Literacy status group of Literate and till 5th standard varied from 0.00% in Anantapur, Chittoor, Krishna, Kurnool, Nellore, Visakhapatnam and Vizianagaram to 1.2% in East Godavari District followed by Cuddapah District 0.8%. The prevalence in the Literacy status group of 6th to 10th standard between 0.0% in Cuddapah, Krishna, Kurnool and Vizianagaram Districts to 0.7% in Srikakulam District beside 0.5% in Visakhapatnam District. The Prevalence in the Literacy Status group of 11th to Graduation varied from 0.00% in 8 Districts are Chittoor, Cuddapah, East Godavari, Kurnool, Nellore, Prakasam, Srikakulam and Vizianagaram District to 0.7% in Anantapur followed by 0.5% in Guntur and West Godavari Districts. And the Prevalence in the Literacy Status group of Post Graduation shown as all the Districts Zero%. The State prevalence 0.7% in Illiterate to 0.0% in Post Graduation.

Table 15: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Literacy Status and Districts, HSS 2014-15

	Illiterate		Literate and till 5th standard		6th to 10th standard		11th to Graduation		Post Graduation	
	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N
Andhra Pradesh	0.7	2499	0.3	3311	0.3	5947	0.2	2913	0.0	371
Anantapur	0.5	212	0.0	370	0.2	407	0.7	134	0.0	54
Chittoor	0.0	133	0.0	120	0.4	565	0.0	329	0.0	47
Cuddapah	1.3	154	0.8	382	0.0	166	0.0	93	0.0	5
East Godavari	0.0	76	1.2	171	0.3	679	0.0	206	0.0	8
Guntur	0.8	262	0.4	224	0.2	489	0.5	201	0.0	22
Krishna	0.0	109	0.0	126	0.0	589	0.3	313	0.0	57
Kurnool	0.6	363	0.0	338	0.0	356	0.0	131	0.0	9
Nellore	0.5	218	0.0	351	0.4	477	0.0	142	0.0	8
Prakasam	1.0	293	0.6	317	0.3	397	0.0	138	0.0	17
Srikakulam	0.0	84	0.5	218	0.7	298	0.0	189	0.0	6
Visakhapatnam	1.7	177	0.0	178	0.5	590	0.2	553	0.0	97
Vizianagaram	0.7	293	0.0	199	0.0	427	0.0	269	0.0	12
West Godavari	1.6	125	0.3	317	0.4	507	0.5	215	0.0	29

5.3. HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Order of Pregnancy

Figure 13: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Order of Pregnancy in Andhra Pradesh , HSS 2014-15

The order of pregnancy denotes the number of times a woman has become pregnant. It includes the number of live births, still births, and abortions. It is also referred to as 'gravidity'. As noted earlier, in the context of HIV, order of pregnancy indicates the duration of exposure to sexual risks, so HIV prevalence among primi-gravida is considered a proxy for new HIV infections and is an indicator of state HIV incidence.

At the state level, 0.1% prevalence among ANC attendees by order of third pregnancy and a High prevalence of 1.6% among women with Fourth or more pregnancy. First time pregnant women prevalence was 0.4% and 0.3% in Second time pregnant women. At the district level, the HIV prevalence among ANC Clinic attendees by order of First Pregnancy, varied from 0.2% in 5 Districts were Anantapur, Krishna, Kurnool, Nellore and Vizianagaram to 0.8% in West Godavari followed by 0.6% in Srikakulam. HIV Prevalence among Second gravida varied between 0.0% in Chittoor, East Godavari, Krishna and Kurnool to 0.8% in Prakasam District followed by Cuddapah 0.7%. HIV prevalence among ANC clinic attendees by order of Third pregnancy is shown only in Kurnool district with 0.5%. The order of Fourth or more Pregnancy HIV Prevalence 0.0% in 10 Districts and 9.1% in Cuddapah District followed by 8.3% in East Godavari and 7.1% in Visakhapatnam District.

Table 16: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Order of Pregnancy in the state of Andhra Pradesh , HSS 2014-15

	First		Second		Third		Fourth or more	
	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N
Andhra Pradesh	0.4	7192	0.3	6268	0.1	1308	1.6	247
Anantapur	0.2	549	0.4	500	0.0	98	0.0	25
Chittoor	0.4	539	0.0	489	0.0	137	0.0	22
Cuddapah	0.4	265	0.7	427	0.0	93	9.1	11
East Godavari	0.5	587	0.0	472	0.0	71	8.3	12
Guntur	0.5	551	0.4	502	0.0	126	0.0	18
Krishna	0.2	638	0.0	470	0.0	74	0.0	9
Kurnool	0.2	538	0.0	421	0.5	184	0.0	55
Nellore	0.2	456	0.3	574	0.0	147	0.0	17
Prakasam	0.4	493	0.8	513	0.0	119	0.0	37
Srikakulam	0.6	480	0.3	287	0.0	27	0.0	4
Visakhapatnam	0.5	795	0.2	661	0.0	111	7.1	28
Vizianagaram	0.2	656	0.2	496	0.0	44	0.0	2
West Godavari	0.8	645	0.2	456	0.0	77	0.0	7

5.4. HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Source of Referral

Figure 14: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Source of Referral in Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

According to the source of referral at state level HIV Prevalence was more in Self Referral (0.5%), Family/ Relatives/ Neighbours/ Friends is (0.4%), Private (Doctor/

Nurses) (0.3%) and Govt (including, ASHA/ ANM) (0.2%) where as no prevalence in ICTC / ART Centres and NGO.

The District-wise HIV prevalence among ANC clinic attendees by Source of Referral were given in the following table 17. The Prevalence in the Source Referral group of Self Referral varied from zero percent in Chittoor, Cuddapah, Krishna, Kurnool, Nellore and Vizianagaram to 1% in West Godavari followed by 0.8% in Visakhapatnam, 0.7% in Prakasam and East Godavari District. HIV prevalence in Referral from Family/Relatives/ Neighbours/ Friends was zero percent in 6 Districts of Anantapur, Chittoor, Cuddapah, Prakasam, Srikakulam and Vizianagaram to 1.7% in West Godavari. Referral from Private (Doctor/Nurses) only seen in Cuddapah District with 4.1%. Referral from Govt. (Including ASHA/ANM) HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic attendees was zero percent in Anantapur, Guntur, Krishna and Kurnool to 0.5% in Cuddapah and East Godavari Districts followed by Srikakulam District 0.4%. Finally, from NGO and ICTC/ART Centre referral HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic attendees was 0.0% in all the Districts.

Table 17: HIV Prevalence (%) among ANC Clinic Attendees by Source of Referral and Districts, HSS 2014-15

	Self Referral		Family/ Relatives/ Neighbors/ Friends		NGO		Private (Doctor/ Nurses)		Govt (including, ASHA/ ANM)		ICTC / ART Centre	
	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N
Andhra Pradesh	0.5	2627	0.4	4112	0	63	0.3	647	0.2	7616	0	17
Anantapur	0.5	617	0	1	0	32	0	1	0	542		
Chittoor	0	190	0	59	0	5	0	340	0.3	604		
Cuddapah	0	62	0	65	0	1	4.1	49	0.5	622		
East Godavari	0.7	139	0.3	789	0	2	0	3	0.5	211		
Guntur	1.3	80	0.6	713			0	2	0	404		
Krishna	0	159	0.2	638					0	397		
Kurnool	0	71	0.5	408			0	26	0	695		
Nellore	0	153	0.4	507	0	14	0	26	0.2	482	0	17
Prakasam	0.7	747	0	115	0	9			0.3	293		
Srikakulam	3	33	0	77			0	1	0.4	688		
Visakhapatnam	0.8	241	0.7	455			0	198	0.3	704		
Vizianagaram	0	35	0	111					0.2	1054		
West Godavari	1	100	1.7	174			0	1	0.2	920		

5.5. HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Place of Residence

Figure 15: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Place of Residence in Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

As per the 2014-15 records, reported the current residence of the respondent as “Urban” or “Rural”. If the current place of residence of the respondent was Municipal Corporation, municipal council, or cantonment area, it was classified as urban. Otherwise, it was recorded as rural.

At the state level, HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic attendees by place of residence in Urban and Rural are both 0.3%. And the District level HIV prevalence among Urban is 0.0% in Krishna, Srikakulam and Vizianagaram Districts to 1.1% in Guntur, and the 0.6% in East Godavari and Nellore followed by 0.5% in Anantapur and Prakasam Districts. On the other hand, the districts currently residing in Rural HIV Prevalence varied between 0.1% in Anantapur, Chittoor, Krishna, Kurnool, and Nellore Districts to 0.8% in Cuddapah, beside Visakhapatnam and West Godavari 0.6%, the districts of 0.6%, 0.5% in Prakasam and Srikakulam District.

Table 18: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Place of Residence and district, HSS 2014-15

	Urban		Rural	
	%	N	%	N
Andhra Pradesh	0.3	4344	0.3	10663
Anantapur	0.5	443	0.1	734
Chittoor	0.2	464	0.1	726
Cuddapah	0.3	304	0.8	495
East Godavari	0.6	170	0.3	968
Guntur	1.1	262	0.2	932

Krishna	0.0	416	0.1	776
Kurnool	0.3	369	0.1	830
Nellore	0.6	331	0.1	863
Prakasam	0.5	388	0.5	766
Srikakulam	0.0	48	0.5	746
Visakhapatnam	0.2	588	0.6	1008
Vizianagaram	0.0	249	0.2	949
West Godavari	0.3	312	0.6	870

5.6. HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Current Occupation of Respondent and District

Figure 16: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Current Occupation of Respondent in Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

At the state level, HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Current Occupation of Respondent were shown in the following table 19, HIV Prevalence is high in Non-Agricultural Labourer with 1% and followed by Agricultural cultivator and Skilled/Semiskilled worker shown 0.5%, Agricultural Labourer 0.4% and finally 0.3% in Housewives. Zero percent in Domestic servant, Petty Business/Small shop, Large Business/ Self employed, Service(Govt/Pvt.), Student, Truck Driver/Helper, Local transport worker and Hotel Staff.

At the District level, the prevalence in Agricultural Labourer varied from 0% in Anantapur, Chittoor, East Godavari, Krishna, Nellore and Vizianagaram to 0.8% in Cuddapah and Prakasam followed by 0.7% in Srikakulam, 0.6% in Guntur and Visakhapatnam, 0.4% in Kurnool District and 0.3% in West Godavari. The Prevalence

in Non-Agricultural Labourer varied from 0% in Chittoor, East Godavari, Guntur, Krishna, Kurnool, Nellore, Prakasam, Vizianagaram and West Godavari to 5.9% in Visakhapatnam beside 5.6% in Anantapur, followed by 2% Cuddapah and 1.1% in Srikakulam District. Prevalence in Skilled/ Semiskilled Worker was shown as 25% in West Godavari district, the remaining 12 districts showed zero percent. HIV prevalence among Agricultural Cultivators was shown as 0.7% in Kurnool District and the remaining 12 district showed Zero%. And the HIV Prevalence among the Housewives varied from 0.0% in Kurnool District to 0.5% in Cuddaph, Prakasam, and West Godavari followed by 0.4% in East Godavari, Guntur, Nellore, Srikakulam and Visakhapatnam District, whereas 0.2% in Anantapur, Chittoor, and Vizianagaram District and finally 0.1% in Krishna District.

Table 19: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Current Occupation of Respondent and district, HSS 2014-15

	Agricultural Laborer		Non-Agricultural Laborer		Domestic Servant		Skilled / Semiskilled worker		Petty business / small shop		Large Business/Self employed		Service (Govt./Pvt.)		Student		Truck Driver/helper		Local transport worker		Hotel Staff		Agricultural cultivator		Housewife	
	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N
Andhra Pradesh	0.4	2539	1.0	418	0.0	26	0.5	188	0.0	51	0.0	31	0.0	379	0.0	62	0.0	2	0.0	1	0.0	26	0.5	208	0.3	11122
Anantapur	0.0	164	5.6	18	0.0	1	0.0	10	0.0	2	0.0	14	0.0	12	0.0	6	0.0				0.0	17	0.0	10	0.2	916
Chittoor	0.0	22	0.0	6			0.0	3	0.0	3			0.0	17	0.0	1	0.0	1							0.2	1142
Cuddapah	0.8	121	2.0	50			0.0	51	0.0	9	0.0	6	0.0	12											0.5	551
East Godavari	0.0	47	0.0	26			0.0	12			0.0	1	0.0	18	0.0	3	0.0				0.0	1	0.0	13	0.4	1022
Guntur	0.6	309	0.0	44	0.0	7	0.0	22	0.0	3			0.0	29	0.0	6					0.0	2	0.0	6	0.4	772
Krishna	0.0	19	0.0	7			0.0	3			0.0	2	0.0	26	0.0	3	0.0	1							0.1	1132
Kurnool	0.4	274	0.0	36	0.0	1	0.0	44	0.0	8			0.0	23	0.0	4					0.0	1	0.7	148	0.0	661
Nellore	0.0	286	0.0	46	0.0	5	0.0	16	0.0	11			0.0	40	0.0	4					0.0	2			0.4	789
Prakasam	0.8	245	0.0	41	0.0	9	0.0	8	0.0	3	0.0	4	0.0	11	0.0	5				0.0	1	0.0	1		0.5	836
Srikakulam	0.7	138	1.1	90			0.0	1	0.0	2			0.0	8	0.0	5									0.4	555
Visakhapatnam	0.6	358	5.9	17	0.0	2	0.0	10	0.0	9	0.0	4	0.0	152	0.0	21									0.4	1020
Vizianagaram	0.0	262	0.0	24	0.0	1	0.0	4	0.0	1			0.0	19	0.0	3					0.0	2	0.0	21	0.2	863
West Godavari	0.3	294	0.0	13			25.0	4					0.0	12	0.0	1							0.0	10	0.5	863

5.7. HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Current Occupation of Respondent's Spouse and District

Figure 17: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Current Occupation of Respondent Spouse Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

At the state level, HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Current Occupation of Respondent Spouse were given in the table 20, HIV Prevalence was high among Hotel Staff with 2.1%, followed by 1.1% among Truck Driver/Helper, 0.5% in Local transport worker and Non-Agricultural Labourer, 0.4% in Skilled/Semiskilled worker, 0.2% Agricultural Labourers and 0.1% in Petty business/ small shop, Agricultural cultivator and Service(Govt/Pvt), Zero percent in Student, Large Business/ Self employed, Unemployed and Domestic Servants.

At the District level, the Prevalence in Agricultural Labourers varied from 0.0% in Anantapur, Chittoor, East Godavari, Guntur, Krishna, Kurnool, and Nellore, to 0.7% in Cuddapah followed by 0.6% in Srikakulam, 0.5% in Prakasam District and 0.3% in Visakhapatnam, Vizianagaram and West Godavari. HIV Prevalence among Non-Agricultural Labourer was 0.0% in Krishna and Vizianagaram District to 1% in Srikakulam followed by 0.8% in East Godavari District, 0.7% in Chittoor, 0.6% in Kurnool, Prakasam and Visakhapatnam, 0.5% in Anantapur and Cuddapah, 0.4% in Guntur and West Godavari and 0.3% in Nellore District. The districts prevalence in Skilled/Semi-skilled workers varied from 0.0% in Kurnool, Nellore, Prakasam, Srikakulam, Visakhapatnam and Vizianagaram district to 1.5% in Cuddapah followed by 1% in Guntur beside 0.9% in East Godavari, Anantapur and West Godavari District and 0.4% in Chittoor and Krishna District. HIV Prevalence among Petty business/ small shop only shown in one district Guntur was 2.0%. HIV Prevalence among Service (Govt./Pvt.) in West Godavari showed 1.4% and 0.2% in Visakhapatnam, Truck Driver/ Helper 6.3% in Cuddapah, 4.8% in Nellore and 4.2% in West Godavari District. HIV Prevalence in Hotel staff was only reported in two districts i.e 12.5% in Guntur and 7.1% in Prakasam District and HIV Prevalence in Agricultural Cultivator only one district found i.e 0.4% in Kurnool District. And HIV Prevalence in Domestic Servant, Large Business/ Self employed, Student and Unemployed was Zero prevalence in all Districts.

Table 20: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Current Occupation of Spouse and district, HSS 2014-15

	Agricultural Labourer		Non-Agricultural Labourer		Domestic Servant		Skilled / Semiskilled worker		Petty business / small shop		Large Business/Self employed		Service (Govt./Pvt.)		Student		Truck Driver/helper		Not Applicable		Local transport worker		Hotel Staff		Agricultural cultivator		Unemployed	
	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N
Andhra Pradesh	0.2	4804	0.5	2747	0	17	0.4	2076	0.1	697	0	340	0.1	2061	0	26	1.1	374	40	5	0.5	1111	2.1	97	0.1	676	0	43
Anantapur	0	532	0.5	185	0	1	0.9	113	0	38	0	42	0	93	0	1	0	36	0	1		72	0	20	0	52	0	4
Chittoor	0	213	0.7	142	0	2	0.4	265	0	107	0	27	0	167	0	2	0	69				95	0	6	0	98		
Cuddapah	0.7	151	0.5	185			1.5	65	0	25	0	63	0	58	0	4	6.3	32				136	0	1	0	79		
East Godavari	0	521	0.8	127	0	1	0.9	213	0	53	0	4	0	110	0	1	0	26	0	1		60	0	6	0	18	0	2
Guntur	0	365	0.4	269	0	1	1	209	2	50	0	6	0	153	0	3	0	15				94	12.5	8	0	20	0	6
Krishna	0	444	0	71			0.4	232	0	73	0	37	0	218	0	3	0	11				96	0	5	0	4		
Kurnool	0	220	0.6	180	0	2	0	214	0	48	0	16	0	116	0	2	0	44				87	0	3	0.4	265		
Nellore	0	343	0.3	311	0	2	0	146	0	68	0	28	0	121	0	2	4.8	21				119	0	11	0	23	0	2
Prakasam	0.5	369	0.6	318	0	7	0	132	0	40	0	28	0	113	0	2	0	25	0	1		103	7.1	14	0	8	0	6
Srikakulam	0.6	310	1	200			0	57	0	35	0	10	0	131			0	9				43	0	1	0	3		
Visakhapatnam	0.3	359	0.6	344	0	1	0	131	0	94	0	50	0.2	474	0	5	0	39	100	2		78	0	4	0	2	0	17
Vizianagaram	0.3	337	0	173			0	185	0	53	0	9	0	238	0	1	0	23				72	0	14	0	90	0	5
West Godavari	0.3	640	0.4	242			0.9	114	0	13	0	20	1.4	69			4.2	24				56	0	4	0	14	0	1

5.8. HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Migration Status of Spouse

Figure 18: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Migration Status of Spouse in Andhra Pradesh, HSS 2014-15

At the state level, HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic attendees by Migration status of spouse is 0.3% in Non-Migrant and on the other side, Migrant HIV prevalence is 0% at the state level and at all the Districts. District level the Prevalence among Non-Migrants varied from 0.1% in Krishna District to 0.6% in Cuddapah District, followed by 0.5% in Prakasam, Srikakulam and West Godavari, and 0.4% in East Godavari and Guntur, the state prevalence equal district with 0.3% in Anantapur, Nellore and Visakhapatnam District. Finally 0.2% in Chittoor, Kurnool and Vizianagarm District.

Table 21: HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees by Migration Status of Spouse and District, HSS 2014-15

	Migrants		Non-Migrants	
	%	N	%	N
Andhra Pradesh	0.0	309	0.3	14673
Anantapur	0.0	69	0.3	1102
Chittoor	0.0	68	0.2	1123
Cuddapah	0.0	19	0.6	774
East Godavari	0.0	12	0.4	1120
Guntur	0.0	15	0.4	1181
Krishna	0.0	6	0.1	1182
Kurnool	0.0	36	0.2	1157
Nellore	0.0	16	0.3	1176
Prakasam	0.0	32	0.5	1131
Srikakulam	0.0	4	0.5	791
Visakhapatnam	0.0	5	0.3	1587
Vizianagaram	0.0	21	0.2	1178
West Godavari	0.0	6	0.5	1171

CHAPTER 6.

Trends of HIV Prevalence among ANC Clinic Attendees

The primary objective of HIV Sentinel Surveillance is to generate data on trends of HIV prevalence among various population groups in the country and state. Over time, HIV Sentinel Surveillance has offered vital clues to newer areas where HIV was emerging, highlighting rising trends in certain Districts or regions.

This has been a critical input to the strategic planning efforts under the National AIDS Control Programme and contributed to shaping the strategies for prevention and control of HIV/AIDS in the state. This chapter presents the trends of HIV prevalence among ANC clinic attendees at state and district levels. Data from the year 2002 has been used for trend analysis. Data from only consistent sites was used for trend analysis as it avoids the effect of addition of new sites on HIV prevalence in subsequent years, and hence provides a better picture of HIV trends in a district. Further, in order to smoothen the sampling variations in HIV prevalence due to small sample size at sentinel site level, a three-year moving average was calculated at state/district levels and trends have been analysed using this data. All the invalid sites i.e. sites where sample size was less than 75% (300) of the target sample size of 400, were excluded from trend analysis for that year.

Though there was a clear declining trend seen in Andhra Pradesh, within the state, there are variations in HIV prevalence among the districts. District level information on HIV is essential for planning district strategies in HIV prevention and control. District wise trend analysis was performed on surveillance data collected during the year 2002-2015 using moving average technique.

6.1. Trends of HIV Prevalence at State Level

Figure 19

6.2. Trends of HIV Prevalence at District Level

Districts with Rising Trends

Figure 20

Figure 21

States with Declining Trends

Figure 22

Figure 23

Figure 24

Figure 25

Figure 26

Figure 27

Figure 28

Figure 29

CHAPTER 7.

Summary

- A total number of 15095 ANCs were recruited and blood samples were collected across 13 districts in the state of Andhra Pradesh during the HSS 2014-15. The median ages of respondents were 22 years in the state. The age distribution was 75.6% in the age group 15-24 years and 23.9% in the age group 25-34 years.
- HIV Prevalence among the age group of 15-24 was 0.27% and the same was 0.52% in 25-49 years age group.
- The proportion of illiterate ANC was 16.6% at the state level and the HIV prevalence among them was 0.7%
- At district level, the proportions of illiterates were varied from 6.7% in East Godavari to 25.2% in Prakasam.
- At the state level, 47.9% of the respondents reported being pregnant for the first time.
- The state level HIV prevalence among ANC clinic attendees in primi-gravida was 0.4%, second gravida was 0.3%, third gravida was 0.1% and in fourth gravida it was 1.6%.
- At the district level, the primi-gravida varies between 33.3% in Cuddapah to 60.2% in Srikakulam.
- Government hospital/ANM/ASHA was identified as the major source of referral to ANC clinics, which accounted for 50.7% of respondents.
- Referrals from the government service providers were higher in the districts of Vizianagaram (87.8%), Srikakulam (86.1%), Cuddapah (77.8%) and West Godavari (77.0%).
- Highest HIV prevalence (0.5%) was seen in people of Self Referrals.
- At the state level, 71.1% of respondents reported to be currently residing in rural areas.
- The HIV Prevalence among both in Urban and Rural was calculated as 0.3%. The urban district with highest HIV prevalence was Guntur (1.1%) and the rural district with highest HIV prevalence was Cudappah (0.8%).

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- At the state level, the majority of the respondents (73.9%) were housewives.
 - 1% of HIV prevalence was seen among the pregnant mothers whose occupations were reported as Non-Agricultural Labourer and 0.5% was the prevalence seen in Skilled / Semiskilled workers.
 - At the state level, accounting for more than one-fourths (31.9%) spouse occupations were Agricultural Labourers. HIV prevalence among them was calculated as 0.2%.
 - HIV Prevalence among the ANCs having their spouse occupation as Hotel Staff was 2.1% and Truck Driver/helper was 1.1%.
 - At the state level, 2.1% of respondents reported that their spouses were migrants. Among them the HIV prevalence was 0%.

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